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S K Saidapur

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#Let'sBeatCoronaTogether

Trends in the 21st Century Education[#]

S K Saidapur*

In nature living beings tend to evolve in response to many prevailing forces operating in the given environment. They essentially struggle, for resources like food, space, and mate. Additionally, it involves overcoming tussle with the neighbors (inter and intra-specific competition for food, space and mate), and also avoid parasites and predators. Thus, predators, parasites and neighbors are 3 major enemies of all forms of life. Who survive at the end? Obviously those that can overcome such challenges survive and/or reproduce. This defines the phrase 'survival of the fittest', a connotation that has no bearing to the physical fitness of an individual. It simply refers to the ability of organisms to leave behind fertile offspring. Such ability is largely due to (1) reshuffling of genes in each generation, (2) selection of useful (including harmless) genes, and (3) elimination of genes that are harmful particularly in early life. This is a very sketchy depiction of how in nature selection pressures work on living beings. Charles Darwin called it natural selection and proposed that through such a mechanism organisms evolve (Theory of Evolution-1958). It is a profound theory with ramifications even outside biological realms. For instance, market or socially driven forces, akin to selection forces in nature, affect evolution of human societies, trade and commerce, industrial production, political rise and fall of individuals, and behaviors like, nepotism, favoritism and corruption in public life. The Universities are also organic entities and they too are affected by the selection forces operating around them at a given point of time. Therefore, scenario of higher education at any given point of time in the history is a reflection of the quality of academicians and educational managers of that time; from faculty of colleges/universities, principals, Vice Chancellors, State Higher Education Ministers, State Councils of Higher Education, UGC, AICTE, IMA, ICAR, ICMR, Bar Council and other regulatory bodies. This prelude is merely to remind ourselves that we must own our responsibilities in addition to crying for our rights.

Evolution of Education System in India

India is indeed the mother of all civilizations as it represents one of oldest surviving of the 45 or so civilizations of the world. She will always be remembered for her many notable contributions in the fields of science and technology, medicine, yoga & meditation, metallurgy, architecture and engineering and more importantly universal message of spirituality to the whole world (Gautier 2013, 2019). India may well have been the world leader in promoting the

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Understanding Plagiarism for Ensuring Quality Original Work

Mushtaq Ahmed I Patel* and Mohasina Anjum A Ansari**

Intentionally using the quotes of others without author's attribution is plagiarism and contributes to illiteracy

-Rain Bojangles

Some authors commit intellectual immorality by stealing ideas, texts, words, formulae, designs or inventions of other authors without attributing to original writer/credit. This is an example of academic dishonesty. Using someone else's work as our own, with or without their full acknowledgment is known as plagiarism. In the present information loaded world, the global IT Wizard, Bill Gates has expressed his views on Plagiarism and calls it as "Intellectual Property Theft". Plagiarism is always not an intentional act; but sometime authors commit it unintentionally as well. Therefore, there is a need for careful and cautious move while referring other works, so as to avoid plagiarism.

Writing scholarly articles and Research Papers is generally supported and supplemented by others' work with proper citation and references. Proper use of the references and supporting material increases authenticity of the articles. Further, creative writing needs mastery over language and thorough knowledge about content, which is a complex task. Regardless of complexity and difficulty involved in creative writing, a number of Ph.Ds., M.Phils., books, articles and research papers are being published in our country everyday. Theoretically these works require good writing skill and creative ideas whereas practically only casual approach of 'cut and paste' is being adopted by many scholars. This is resulting in write-ups that are unethical which in itself is plagiarism. An article or a book is an asset for the author just like money, jewellery, vehicle, and property etc. This asset of author is purely based on originality of the creation. If someone wants to use the idea of another author,

then one can put the idea as a reference of other and explain the idea in one's own way to support or argument/explanation. Due to knowledge and information explosion in the form of books and Internet websites, the writers are easily copying the material in their writing. Plagiarism has become a serious issue at higher educational institutions for works involving project reports, articles and other research papers. This use of creative work of others without acknowledging the author needs to be examined, so as to bring a remedy for improving quality of research and writing.

Historical Perspective

According to Pennycook (1996) the text ownership or authorship is a western notion. He also identifies three dominant paradigms of plagiarism as pre-modern, modern and post-modern (Kearney,1998). Before modern era it was believed that the knowledge belonged to God and benefitted whole society. In post-modern era western thinking replaced God with human as the source of imagination (Introna et al, 2003) cited in Dahlia (2009). According to Mallon (1989) cited by Park, C (2003) the Elizabethan playwright Ben Johnson was the first person to use the word plagiarist, which mean literary theft at the beginning of the 17th century. The word 'Plagiarism' is derived from the Latin word 'Plagiare' which means 'to kidnap or abduct'. What Thomas (2000) called 'textual misappropriations' 'became much more common as mass produced books, became more widely available and there was more material to steal from (Park C, 2003). Barnhart (1998, p.801) traces the etymology of the word plagiarism ('literary theft') from the earlier English word plagiarist ('one who wrongfully takes another's words or ideas), derive from the Latin plagiarus ('kidnapper, literary thief') from plagium (kidnapping) from plaga (Park C 2003, p-472). Some rhetoric of plagiarism are 'the unoriginal sin' (Colon, 2001), 'Sin... against originality' (Anonymous, 1997) and 'a writer's worst sin' (Miller, 1993), 'a cancer that erodes the rich legacy of scholarship' (Park C 2003, p-472).

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All the above definitions of plagiarism are pointing towards unethical, immoral act which involves stealing of others work and presenting it as our own. Even though ideas, concepts and words are not tangible items but stealing of these is also a crime. The consequence of this crime is very dangerous for the whole world of academics as this directly snubs the creativity and originality of budding writers and researchers.

Types of Plagiarism

Basically, plagiarism is a process of stealing others work but it has different ways through which intentionally or unintentionally the people are committing this folly. Types of Plagiarism is depicted in Figure-1. Types of plagiarism mentioned by Theresa Ireton (2009) are discussed below. These types give us an idea where and how plagiarism occurs, so that novel writers can avoid to commit these mistakes.

Fig. 1. Types of Plagiarism

- **Plagiarism of Structure:** Paraphrasing others' words by changing sentence construction that is just by using synonyms for the existing content. For example, many research scholars are very easily paraphrasing the content of other authors even scholars are paraphrasing the whole dissertation available on the websites and submitting the same. Internet is playing an instrumental role in the whole process of stealing.
- **Plagiarism of Ideas:** This is taking away others' ideas as one's own without giving the person credit that means the whole idea of someone is stolen without acknowledging the main author. For example, the debutante Harvard student Kaavya Viswanathan was hoping for her first book, How Opal Mehta Got Kissed, Got Wild and Got a Life, was pulled down for being very similar to author

Megan McCafferty's book Sloppy First and Second Helpings. Some of entertainers like film makers are accused of using others' ideas without proper acknowledgment.

- **Plagiarism of Authorship:** This is tuning in a replication of others' work which also means reproducing others' work without their consent.
- **Plagiarism of Self:** The use of one's own previous work for a new assignment. The use of previous original work in one's own new assignment is plagiarism of self-work. For example, a Rhodes Scholar with a writing job at The New Yorker, Lehrer was a rising star in the literary world. In June 2012, a few writers noticed that Lehrer had recycled some of his own previous material in several new blog posts for The New Yorker. The investigations on his new works resulted in a finding that Lehrer just modified his quotes in his Bob Dylan book, "Imagine," and plagiarized material in his writing for Wired.
- **Reverse Plagiarism:** It refers to falsely giving authorship credit over a work to a person who did not author it, or falsely claiming a source supports that the source does not exist. There is rare incident of reverse plagiarism cases in literature and serious research. However, some students do this kind of plagiarism when they don't get the relevant source for references. The advent of social media like WhatsApp has increased reverse plagiarism. A few Urdu couplets are found to be attributed unknowingly to famous Urdu Poet Ghalib who originally did not author it.

Fig 2. Showing Methods of Plagiarism in ICT Era

- **Accidental Plagiarism:** Usually students commit this mistake in hurry. They unintentionally paraphrase and forget to mention the source or neglect proper citation etc. But anyway, whether it is intended or unintended this act is considered

as a theft and consequent material is known to be plagiarised.

Further another author Ramesh C. Gour has presented different techniques of plagiarism through which this intellectual crime is being carried out in the higher education institutions in present Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) era (Figure-2).

- i. *Clone*: The cloning is submitting others' work, word-to-word, as one's own for example just replacing original author's name by own name.
- ii. *CTRL-C*: This type of copied material contains significant portions of text from a single source without alterations. In this a part of the text is copied as it is and pasted in the document without attributing the author.
- iii. *Find – Replace*: Here writer uses changing key words and phrases but retaining the essential content of the source is another way. Here the text changes but idea remains same, and original author is replaced by some other name.
- iv. *Remix*: The writer paraphrases from multiple sources, makes it to fit together. That means writer is paraphrasing different text of different authors with same theme and claiming as own.
- v. *Recycle*: Here one borrows generously from the writer's previous work without citation. This means repeating the same ideas of previous writing of one's own in new writing.
- vi. *Mash up*: Mixes copied material from multiple sources this means copying from different sources but on single theme and claiming as own. It is difficult to detect such plagiarism easily.
- vii. *404 Error*: Includes citations to non-existent or inaccurate information about sources this means giving improper references about the information.
- viii. *Aggregator*: Includes proper citation to sources but the paper contains almost no original work. According to this the author is simply giving the reference without using the information in the paper.

The increased publication business in present circumstances has increased such ICT oriented plagiarism.

Plagiarism Perspective in Global Context

The rules and policies of plagiarism vary from country to country. According to Glendenning (2013) in Germany, it is mentioned in an unpublished report that 40 per cent of respondents admitted that they regularly cut and paste from sources without citing and referencing. In Impact of Policies for Plagiarism in Higher Education Across Europe (IPPHEAE) survey 11 per cent teachers admitted they may have accidentally or deliberately plagiarised at some time previously. At post-graduation level they have set percentage-wise plagiarism and their respective actions to be taken. In France also a set pattern is there for plagiarism for example depending on percentage of content plagiarised, appropriate action is suggested, and more and more French universities are adapting anti-plagiarism software. The United Kingdom's Quality Assurance Agency (QAA) for Higher Education is more stringent. The Agency includes fraud, collusion, cheating, impersonation, and the use of 'inadmissible material' in their definition of 'academic misconduct'. This includes material which is downloaded from the Internet without proper acknowledgment. Copyright is a property right that gives the owner the exclusive right to exploit a work. The Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988 (CDPA 1988) governs UK copyright law. One of the main differences between copyright and plagiarism is that copyright generally does not protect ideas, only the expression of those ideas.

Chinese pedagogy is influenced by Confucius and according to Confucius teachings, students are taught to respect those who provide knowledge. In China, students are expected to memorize and repeat classical text in school. Students are made to understand that knowledge belong to society as a whole and not to the individual alone. They are also taught that it is a disrespect to their teachers or readers if they cite their sources as this may imply that he or she did not already know the source. But technically theft of intellectual property is illegal in China. A study by Ramzan et al. (2012) reveals that Pakistan's graduate and postgraduate students fall into society and family pressures to get higher grades, and thereby improve achievement which in turn helps in getting employment and better status in the society. Due to these pressures, students get involved in unfair means such as plagiarism, as a short cut to perform better in exams and also they

produce greater number of publications of their works. It is not enough to create only awareness among the students about plagiarism or train them to improve their writings, the society should stop pressurizing the students for good marks or good jobs they should encourage for true learning and provoke for creative thinking. Tayraukham (2009) cited by Ramzan et al. (2012), conducted a study in Thailand where they found that students plagiarized to gain prestige in society and jobs. When under pressure, a significant number of students responded that plagiarism is the last resort to come up to the university expectations to publish research and complete assignments in time. The burden assigned to students by teachers in the form of lengthy assignment, a greater number of publications and project reports expected within a stipulated time frame are motivating students to resort for short cut methods of plagiarism.

Context of Plagiarism in India

Plagiarism exists in various forms in India. We need to understand the causes of plagiarism and try to solve these problems. When we closely look at the education system of the country, it is found that Plagiarism does not start at higher level of education, seeds are sown in childhood at primary and secondary level. During primary schooling, teachers asks the student to write the answer as exactly as in the text book, otherwise there is a threat to lose marks. This practice is gradually leading the minds of student just to memorise from books and reproduce in the exams. Students think textbooks are ultimate source of error free content. When students enter higher education, they carry forward in their mind habit of memorization and copying from books. Thus, they cannot write on their own and unintentionally commit the offence of plagiarism.

Tools and Techniques to overcome Plagiarism

Dawson and Overfield (2006) found that students were aware that plagiarism is bad, but they were not clear of what constitutes plagiarism and how to avoid it. Just announcing the penalties and actions about the plagiarism among students cannot stop them from committing this mistake, they need to understand the severity of this offence, for which there is a need to plan proper strategies and create awareness among the students. First of all, at lower level of education like primary and secondary,

more emphasis should be given on writing skill and creative writing that makes them confident in writing. Teachers should encourage students for writing on their own rather than precisely copying from textbook. If someone writes by one's own, he/she will understand the importance of own write-up and others as well and thereby they will never like to borrow someone else's writing or idea without proper attribution.

Plagiarism can also be curbed by using Plagiarism detecting software, in which a file can be uploaded in the software, then the software compares the content of uploaded file with other files on the Internet and then gives the result of plagiarised material. According to Jagadish, J and Venkatesh (2016) following are the plagiarism Tools for detection of similarity of Contents: i. Ithenticate, California, USA. ii. Turnitin, California, USA iii. Write Check, California, USA vi. Viper, England v. Plag Aware, Ulm, Germany vi. Plag Scan, Germany vii. Urkund, Sweeden viii. Docoloc, Germany ix. Plagiarism Checker X, New York, USA x. Plag Tracker, Ukrainian xi. Nitya D' Arch, Kottayam/Cochin, Kerala.

Laws Concerned with Plagiarism in India

Ideas, writing and quotes are abstract things, therefore stealing these things is unethical deed or immoral activity. Persons copying this cannot be punished like general punishment given for stealing of objects or money etc. However, this is an academic crime which is leading towards poor quality of research and snubbing the creative writing; therefore, it has to stop. This academic crime is more in Higher Education Institutions of India, therefore the Highest decision-making body like University Grant Commission has approved *Promotion of Academic Integrity and Prevention of Plagiarism in Higher Educational Institution Regulation 2018*. The UGC released the regulation on 23rd July 2018 for students, faculty, researchers and staff of all Higher Educational Institutions in India with immediate enforcement. If these regulations are followed to certain extent the intensity of plagiarism can be decreased.

The UGC regulation is based on four tiers or levels of plagiarism, in which the document, report or article is checked by percentage of plagiarised content (Figure-3). The first level is Level 0 in which the content "similarities up to 10 per cent," would

carry no penalty for both student and faculty. The second level is Level 1, in which 10 per cent to 40 per cent of a document is plagiarized, would require students to submit a revised manuscript (thesis) and faculty members to withdraw the plagiarized paper. The third level is Level 2 in which 40 per cent to 60 per cent of the document is plagiarized, a student would be suspended for a year and the faculty member would be penalised as loss of pay raise for one year and prohibited from supervising students for 2 years. The fourth level is Level 3 in which if more than 60 per cent is plagiarized then his/her thesis would be removed from the program and registration is cancelled. In case of teaching faculty concerned would lose of 2 years of pay increments and a 3-year ban on supervising students.

In addition to these the higher education institutions have to form a Departmental Academic Integrity Panel (DAIP) and Institutional Academic Integrity Panel (IAIP) to investigate the plagiarism cases by academic community of the institution. The HRD Ministry has also announced the introduction of 'Turnitin' software to curb plagiarism, at Ph.D. Before submitting the Ph.D. Thesis, it is being examined through Turnitin software to ensure plagiarism free thesis. Curbing of plagiarism may work if all the Universities in India start using such software and this will result in encouragement of original work.

Conclusion

Plagiarism is an academic dishonesty, an intellectual immorality and literary theft. It is really helpful for students and faculties who want Ph.Ds and publications without any effort with less time. Thus, it is also leading our scholars' towards stealing of others works without feeling guilty. Plagiarism snubs the creativity of individuals and finishes the originality of work. Internet must become facilitator in reference and creation of original thoughts avoiding literary theft. We are aware that India is producing a greater number of Ph.Ds. and thousands of publications every year and the graph is growing at higher side only. The quantity of the research work is increasing but the quality is not improving. The creative writing skill is getting snubbed and the whole academic atmosphere is getting polluted by this intellectual crime. To overcome the issue of Plagiarism UGC has taken some initiatives and released the regulations to the higher education institutions which can curb plagiarism and promotes the clean and healthy academic environment. This is high time when the plagiarism which has polluted the higher education needs a proper treatment. Hence, the UGC regulation for Promotion of Academic Integrity and Prevention of Plagiarism in Higher Education Institutions are to be strictly adhered to. We have to build a plagiarism free academic environment for our future researchers whose innovative ideas

Fig. 3. Four Levels of Plagiarism according to UGC (2018)

Four Levels of Plagiarism							
Level 0		Level 1		Level 2		Level 3	
10 % Similarity		10 % to 40% Similarity		40 % to 60 % Similarity		Above 60%	
Student/Researcher	Faculty	Student/Researcher	Faculty	Student/Researcher	Faculty	Student/Researcher	Faculty
No Penalty	No Penalty	To submit a revised script within a stipulated time period not exceeding 6 months	To withdraw the plagiarized paper	Debarred from submitting a revised script for a period of one year	He / She would forfeit the annual pay raise and prohibited supervising student for 2 years	Registration for that programme shall be cancelled	He/She would be extended to lose of pay increase for 2 years and 3 years ban for supervising students

will contribute to the education system of India and abroad.

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COVID-19 CONCERN

An Appeal to Readers

The outbreak of COVID-19 commonly known as Novel Corona Virus has engulfed the entire world. The pandemic has emerged as one of the biggest ever faced by the human race. With great concern, University News appeals to its subscribers and readers to stay alert and cooperate with the government in adhering to all the social and health advisories issued from time to time. By being careful and cautious, we can beat the virus by breaking the chain and prevent it from spreading further.

We wish all the citizens of India, our subscribers and readers the best of safety and health, and appeal to each one of us to show solidarity in this hour of adversity.

#LetsBeatCoronaTogether
Stay Alert, Stay Safe

EDITOR